

NEW UZBEKISTAN THE IMPORTANCE OF FURTHER STRENGTHENING THE PLACE OF YOUTH IN POLITICAL PROCESSES

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Annotation.

The article analyzes the participation of young people of New Uzbekistan in political processes. The author has shown that young people have a special status not only as an important subject in the life of society and the country, but also in political processes. The article made several proposals to strengthen the position of youth in political processes based on international experience.

Key words: youth, public administration, political processes, electoral process, youth organizations, social networks, digital platform, innovation ideas. Introduction. As you know, the first legislative act signed by Shavkat Mirziyoyev as President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in order to increase youth participation in political, economic and social processes is the law "On State Youth Policy" dated September 14, 2016. After all, the head and government of our state are well aware that the most important factor determining Uzbekistan's place among the most developed countries in the world is attention to youth. Comprehensive reforms are being implemented in order to modernize the country in a new way, economic development, ensure the openness of society and strengthen international cooperation in various fields. The role of youth in political processes plays an important role and is considered crucial in carrying out this work, as well as plays a major role in shaping the future of the country.

Today, young people make up one fifth of the world's population. Most of them are in developing countries. Representatives of this generation face problems such as limited use of natural resources, education, employment and broad economic opportunities.

Research methodology. Knowledge about political processes, legislation and public administration has a positive impact on the political activities of young people. Some of the young people stand out as political leaders and are actively involved in solving mature problems in society.

Instead of information, the majority of Uzbekistan's population is made up of young people. According to the State Statistics Committee for 9 months of 2024, the number of young people in Uzbekistan aged 14 to 35 years is about 11 million people, which means that about 30% of the total population is young people .

In political processes, age is indicated as the age if it does not exceed 40 years. Youth and young citizens should not be treated as the same group. For example, young people born in the information age are considered as the “digital generation”. However, although they do not make up the majority, it is wrong to classify the youth of the South of the world in this category. In particular, in southern and south-eastern sub-Saharan Africa, more than 20% of young people do not even know how to read and write, while the literacy gap between urban and rural populations increases significantly from year to year.

The international community considers the participation of young people in public administration and political processes to be important. In particular, this recognition has found expression in a number of UN resolutions. The United Nations Development Programme views youth as a socially transformative force and aims to help increase their participation in public administration.

In order to further strengthen the place of youth in the political processes of Uzbekistan, various youth organizations are operating. In particular, through the Youth Parliament, the Youth Affairs Agency, the Youth Union, deputy khokims of all levels on youth issues and youth leaders in government organizations and organizations equivalent to them, young people have the opportunity to raise their problems and proposals at the state level.

In particular, the number of young deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, the highest body, is 10 people, 60 young people were nominated as candidates for deputies in the elections on October 27, 2024. Also in 2020, a youth parliament was established under the Senate and the Legislative Assembly. They act to protect the interests of young people and increase the influence of young people on public policy.

According to an analysis of public administration leaders conducted in 2023, 8 of the 21 ministers (38 percent) were between the ages of 35 and 45, 5 (24 percent) were between 46 and 50, and 3 (14 percent) were between 51 and 55 . The composition of local self-government bodies has also been significantly updated. In particular, Assistant to the President, Deputy Speaker, Minister of Preschool and School Education, Ambassador to the UAE, Director of the Youth Agency, Chairman of the Tourism Committee, head of the Republican Center for

Spirituality and Education, Director of the Agency for the Development of Innovations, etc.

In recent years, young people in Uzbekistan have been actively involved in political processes, actively participate in political processes and express their views through social networks. According to a 2023 study, more than 70 percent of young people followed political processes through social media .

In Uzbekistan, there is a lot of social activity among young people under the age of 30, interest in entrepreneurship and IT spheres, which are growing rapidly. Despite the fact that more than 5,000 youth jobs were created through the Youth Affairs Agency of Uzbekistan in 2023, the unemployment rate among young people cannot be called low. In particular, in 2022-2023, youth unemployment was 15-17 percent. This figure is 7-8 percent in Kazakhstan, 9-11 percent in Russia, 30 percent in the EU and 7-8 percent in the United States .

Conclusion. The participation of Uzbekistan's youth in political processes is a very important factor in the country's sustainable development. Therefore, our President Sh. Mirziyoyev said:" We will definitely build a new Uzbekistan together with you, with the youth of our entire country." Youth activism ensures the democratic development of the political system and acts as the main force in the process of modernization of the country. Therefore, it would not be an exaggeration to say that a state policy that takes into account the problems and interests of youth, as well as support for our youth on all fronts, is the solid foundation of our new Uzbekistan.

Suggestions. The involvement of young people in active participation in political processes is becoming important, as it affects their future and the development of society. In particular, the work performed should be in formats that correspond to the interests of young people and inspire them. In particular, developed countries pay special attention to educational and educational programs when involving young people in political processes. For example, in the Scandinavian country, young people gain knowledge about civic responsibility, public administration and political processes from school. Therefore, it is also necessary to expand civic education programs in secondary and higher educational institutions in Uzbekistan, to teach young people to understand responsibility in political processes.

These proposals will promote the participation of the youth of the New Uzbekistan in political processes and strengthen their role in society.

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